

Enrichment of university bibliography data for open science monitoring

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Introduction

With the increased uptake of Open Science practices, Open Science monitoring becomes more relevant as well. As Open Science differs across scientific disciplines, the Berlin University Alliance (BUA) Open Science Dashboards project¹ aims to develop discipline specific Open Science indicators. One part of the project is the development of an Open Science Dashboard for the Department of Earth Sciences at the Freie Universität Berlin.

To start with, the Open Science Dashboard for the Department of Earth Sciences at the Freie Universität Berlin (FU) will include information on PID availability, open access category and copyright/open licence status of publication output of the Department of Earth Sciences of the years 2016-2022. The data base for the dashboard was obtained from the FU university bibliography², but coverage of Persistent Identifier (PID) information was incomplete, open access category information was incomplete and often erroneous, and copyright/open licence information was missing in this data set.

Therefore, the data set was enriched with manually researched information. Data enrichment was different for journal articles and for non-journal-article publications. For journal articles, copyright/open licence information was added and open access category information was checked and added or corrected. For non-journal-article publications, missing PIDs were added and open access category information was checked and added or corrected. All non-journal-article research output was classified as follows:

- Books (academic publications; these include monographs, edited volumes, text books) NOT included in this category are schoolbooks.
- Book chapters (a chapter in an edited volume or textbook)
- Conference abstracts (a published abstract for a conference presentation, it can be included in a conference abstracts book or published as a separate entry on the conference website)
- Conference paper (a short paper included in conference proceedings)
- Other (when another category is not applicable, this category should be assigned (for example book reviews, project reports, blog posts, chapters in a school book etc.).)

Definition of Open Access Categories

The role of Open Access publishing as an element of Open Science has become central to science management and research policy in recent years. Open access publications are monitored worldwide by many initiatives, but it is crucial to define what exactly is meant by open access. Open access publications may be published with different characteristics. These characteristics are often described in terms of categories, the most common being Diamond, Gold, Green, Hybrid, Platinum, and Bronze.³ Also, Blue and Black open access categories are described.⁴ However, with increasing publication types, models, and venues, and journals flipping from traditional, closed access to open access, these categories become more and more complex to use and need to be thoroughly defined.

¹ Duine M. 2022.

² Freie Universität Berlin University Bibliography

³ see e.g., Piwowar H. 2018, Priem J. 2021.

⁴ Schmeja S. 2018.

The definitions of open access categories are made for journal articles and for non-journal-article publications.

Journal Articles

Gold Open Access

Gold articles have all the same characteristics as Hybrid articles (inclusive Creative Commons licence), but are published in all-open access journals, which are in turn called "Gold journals", or just "OA journals".

Green Open Access

Green articles are published in toll-access journals, but archived in an open access archive, or repository. These repositories may be discipline-specific (like ArXiv) or institutional repositories operated by universities or other institutions. Green open access articles may be published versions, postprints (=final drafts), or preprints, and can have any licence or no licence.

Bronze Open Access

Bronze open access articles are originally described as "articles made free-to-read on the publisher website, without an explicit Open license"⁵, and a similar description of Bronze articles is provided by Unpaywall: "Bronze articles are free to read on the publisher's website, without a license that grants any other rights. There may be a delay between publication and availability to read, and often articles can be removed unilaterally by the publisher."⁶ However, the category of "Bronze OA" is far from comprehensively defined: "Bronze is relatively little-discussed in the OA literature, and suggests that this OA category deserves further attention from the OA community."⁷ For the purpose of this investigation, we have expanded the scope of Bronze open access according to the following scheme:

Bronze articles are free to read on the publisher's website, without a licence that grants any other rights. There may be a delay between publication and availability to read, and often articles can be removed unilaterally by the publisher.

- Bronze articles may be also articles where the version of record on the publisher's website is not available, but the publisher makes the final draft on the publisher's website available, with a bespoke licence (=not a Creative Commons licence). Example: "© 2017. This manuscript version is made available under the Elsevier user license" <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2017.04.012>
- Bronze articles may be available on the publisher's website (Version of record, VoR), free to read and to download, but with a bespoke licence (=not a Creative Commons licence). Example: "This is an article distributed under the terms of the [Science Journals Default License](https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat3185)." <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.aat3185>
- Bronze articles may be available on the publisher's website (Version of record), free to read and to download, but with the copyright belonging to the journal, publisher, or journal-owning academic society. To qualify for "Hybrid OA", the article must have, in our definition, a Creative Commons Licence. Example: "©2019. American Geophysical Union. All Rights Reserved." <https://doi.org/10.1029/2018TC005297>

⁵ Piwowar H. 2018.

⁶ Priem J. 2021.

⁷ Piwowar H. 2018.

- Bronze articles may also be published on a personal website. Example: https://offtheshelfedge.files.wordpress.com/2017/10/stright_etal_2017_mpg_modelling_chi_le.pdf
- Journal articles that are available via illegal pirate sites, e.g. SciHub, or articles from Academic Social Networks (ASN) are not considered as Bronze.

Hybrid Open Access

Hybrid articles are free to read at the time of publication, with a Creative Commons licence, in journals that publish open access as well as subscription-based articles.

Remark: Green vs. Bronze

If a Green version and a Bronze version are available, the article is tagged Green, even if the Bronze version is the Version of Record (VoR) and the Green version is a postprint or preprint (exception see below for Bronze VoR articles on publishers websites).

Example: <https://doi.org/10.1080/00206814.2016.1233834>; Green version (accepted author manuscript (AAM) in an institutional repository): https://eprints.keele.ac.uk/id/eprint/2170/1/Halama_et_al_Nitrogen_accepted_MS.pdf. Bronze version: Version of record on Research Gate, “© 2016 Informa UK Limited, trading as Taylor & Francis Group” https://www.researchgate.net/publication/308998090_Fluid-induced_breakdown_of_white_mica_controls_nitrogen_transfer_during_fluid-rock_interaction_in_subduction_zones

Exception to the above rule: When a Green version and a Bronze version are available, the article is tagged Bronze, in case the Bronze version is the Version of Record on the publishers website and free to read and to download. This is the case when a journal flipped from hybrid to full open access: all articles that were “closed” when the journal was still in hybrid publication mode are today available in open access, with copyright by the publisher and without any open licence. Articles that were published in open access when the journal was still in hybrid publication mode are today available in open access, with open licence, just as it has been at the time of publication of the respective article.

Example: Geophysical Research Letters is a fully open access journal as of 1 January 2023. Before, it was a hybrid journal, offering subscription content and the option for full open access articles with article processing charges. Consequently, a subscription article from, e.g., 2017 is available today open access (VoR, labelled “free access”), with copyright by the publisher and without any open licence, on the publisher’s website. Such an article is tagged “Bronze” in our definition. This very article may be available with a VoR in a trusted repository or another place, e.g. ResearchGate, but nevertheless, we consider such article “Bronze”. Example: VoR on publisher’s website: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/2017GL073683>; VoR in a trusted repository: https://gfzpublic.gfz-potsdam.de/rest/items/item_2230911_4/component/file_2446888/content

Non-journal-article publications

Gold Open Access

Gold open access publications are final publications, published free to read on the publisher’s or conference organiser’s website and include a Creative Commons licence.

Green Open Access

Green open access publications - or self-archiving - are published free to read in an open access repository or on the author's website. They can have any licence, or no license.

Bronze Open Access

Bronze publications are final publications, published free to read and do not include a Creative Commons license. They may include other licences or a copyright notice.

Closed publications are not free to read. Publications that appeared in print only should also be assigned this category. When a Creative Commons licence was applied, this information was listed as well.

Addition of Persistent Identifiers

When a Persistent Identifier was missing, it was researched online: either on the author's personal website, the conference website or the publishers' website. Any researched PID was included, and when not available, the url was included. When a publication has appeared in print only and the ISBN is available, this was added as well.

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